

MODULAR-BASED INSTRUCTION PREPAREDNESS OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN SANTA CRUZ DISTRICT AMIDST THE PANDEMIC

DOLORA CALASICAS MARISTELA¹

AUGUST V. TUIZA²

dolora.maristela@deped.gov.ph¹

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7779-7511>¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus

ABSTRACT

Modular learning is currently used by all public schools in the country as face-to-face engagements are restricted due to COVID-19 Pandemic. The objective of this study lies in evaluating the preparedness of Elementary School Teachers in Santa Cruz District for module-based learning. It determined whether the instructors can effectively impart knowledge to their students despite the constraints posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. This research used descriptive research design and forty – two (42) elementary teachers of Santa Cruz District, Laguna were selected for this study. The researcher tried to find the status of preparedness of teachers in terms of health, resources and interaction. It was analyzed using percentage and factor analyses. The overall mean of the teacher's health preparedness is 4.65. Health preparedness has one factor which accounts for 55.40% variance. The teachers are very prepared with regard to their health. The best indicators of this are the statements, "Have full understanding of the topic I am teaching", "Always have a positive outlook in life", and "Always attend webinars regarding modular teaching." Health preparedness is strongly associated with the items, "I am physically fit.", and "I am always prepared physically, mentally, and emotionally." Regular health evaluation of the instructors will help in knowing their conditions that would in turn provide support to reduce stress brought upon by the pandemic. The overall mean of the teacher's preparedness in terms of resources is 4.65. Resource preparedness has one factor which accounts for 80.90% variance. The teachers are very prepared in terms of resources and the three best indicators of these are the statements, "Make sure to check all my students' activity whenever I can", "Make sure that the resources provide learning that is suited to the learner's reading skills", and "Make sure that the resources are reliable and impart knowledge effectively." On the other hand, resource preparedness is related to the items, "Make sure that the resources are reliable and impart knowledge effectively," and "make sure that I personally check and assess the activity I made before handling them to my students." Further support may provide to the teachers in the delivery of learning exemplars and retrieval of learning assessments. The support can be in terms of additional protection or assistance from the local government when they deliver exemplars and retrieve learning assessments. The overall mean of the teacher's preparedness in terms of interaction is 4.56. Interaction preparedness has one factor which accounts for 59.30% variance. The teachers are very prepared with their interaction with their pupils. The best indicators of this are, "Inform the parents about their child's academic performance", "Maintain a good relationship with the students' parents", and "Make sure to answer all the queries/ question of the parents/guardian regarding the task given to their children." Interaction preparedness of teachers is strongly associated with the items, "Approach a student and try to solve the issue if he/she has a problem.", and "I make sure to have a harmonious relationship with the parents/ guardian." Constant communication

between the teachers, parents, and students was key to a successful implementation of modular-based instruction. In order to determine its association with the frequencies of learning assessments, Chi – square test for independence was used. It concluded that the status of preparation of teachers in terms of health, resources and interaction was independent of frequency of learning assessments. With respect to activity sheets, 57.1% of the teachers require their pupils to submit these learning assessments once a week. It appears that the date of submission of a particular learning assessment depends on the teacher. The learning activity sheets may encompass the lessons for the modules covered and should substantially help the students in applying the knowledge acquired. In terms of performance tasks, 52.4% of the teachers require their pupils to submit such tasks once a week while about 12% of these teachers require their pupils to submit them twice a month. Most of the surveyed teachers give out performance tasks once a week. The frequencies vary from daily to once a month. Performance tasks may relate to the lessons tackled and must be able to measure the proficiency of the students. With respect to summative tests, 26.2% of the teachers have this type of assessment twice a month and almost 12% of them have a weekly summative test. Most of the surveyed teachers give out summative test twice a month. The frequencies vary from never to once a week. Summative test assesses the learnings of student after every instructional unit. It was recommended to administer summative test once a month. There is no sufficient statistical evidence to conclude that the status of preparation of teachers in terms of health, resources and interaction was dependent on frequency of learning requirements. The status of preparation of teachers in terms of health, resources and interaction was independent of the frequency of learning requirements. Future parallel studies regarding the preparedness of teachers and learning assessments can be conducted. Variables like years of experience of teachers, age, sex, the type of seminars they have attended and the status of submission of learning assessments can be included. Based on the findings and conclusion made by the researchers here are the recommendations based on the above – mentioned findings and conclusion. Further support must be provided to the teachers in the delivery of learning exemplars and retrieval of learning assessments. The support can be in terms of additional protection or assistance from the local government when they deliver exemplars and retrieve learning assessments. Even though, teachers are prepared, health, interaction and resource – wise, they still need additional support in order to reduce stress brought upon by the pandemic. Frequency of learning requirements must always be considered. The learners have multiple subjects. So, if all requirements have to be submitted daily then the learners may not only suffer extreme difficulty in doing and submitting all of them and the quality of their work may also be affected. Consider preparing a relaxed schedule of submission of requirements. It was a fact that the teachers are prepared resource, interaction and health – wise. But they still have to be provided with webinars that seek to further their preparedness or address their mental health. Help teachers update skills in module writing through webinars. Encourage them to inspire and motivate their learners during this time of pandemic. Modify the quantity of learning assessments. Reduce them to a very manageable amount. Also, enhance the quality of the content of the module. The discussion of the lesson together with the learning assessments must be fit the level of understanding of the learners. In this way, the learners may be able to complete the needed learning assessments of each module. Future parallel studies regarding the preparedness of teachers and learning assessments can be conducted. Variables like years of experience of teachers, age, sex, the type of seminars they have attended and the status of submission of learning assessments can be included. The study could focus on the relationship of teachers' preparedness and other related variables to the status of submission of learning assessments.

Keywords: Distance learning modalities, Modular-based Instruction, Preparedness of Teachers, health, resources and interaction preparedness, Activity Sheets, Summative Test and Performance Tasks.